

GENE NAME	Gene ID	Forward primer 5' to 3'	Reverse primer 5' to 3'	Reference
<i>SLGA20OX1</i>	<i>Solyc03g006880</i>	GAGTTGATGCTAATCTCATTCT	CAACTATGTGAGATGATTCTTTC	Matsuo et al ., 2019
<i>SLGA20OX3</i>	<i>Solyc11g072310</i>	TGGCCGGACCATGAGAAGCCAA	CCCTAGAGAAAAGGTGCTCACGGCA	
<i>PROCERA</i>	<i>Solyc11g011260</i>	CAGGGGATTGTGTGCTAATT	CTCAACAAGAGTAACAATCTTC	
<i>SLGA2OX1</i>	<i>Solyc02g070430</i>	TGGCCCTGCTAACCCTTTTGGCT	GGGATCAGGTGGGACTGAGATCCA	
<i>SLGA2OX2</i>	<i>Solyc07g056670</i>	TGGCGATTGTGGTCGGGTCGAA	TCAGCCTGAAAACGGAGTCGCT	
<i>SLGA2OX5</i>	<i>Solyc10g007570</i>	GGACATTGGATTCTGTCCACCT	TGTACAAGCTGTCTTCATCCCCT	
<i>SAND</i>	<i>SGN- U316474/SL AT2G28390</i>	TTGCTTGGAGGAACAGACG	GCAAACAGAACCCCTGAATC	Expósito-Rodríguez et al., 2008

Supplementary Table S1: Gene abbreviations, genomic accession numbers, Forward and Reverse primers used for the qPCR test. References to the previous studies using the same primers.

Supplementary Figure S1: Comparison of the equatorial perimeters and E1 cell length at the anthesis stage ovaries and 40 DAP M82 and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* fruits. **A; D:** Box plots showing the perimeter distributions computationally measured from equatorial sections of the ovary of M82 (blue) and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (dark-green) at the anthesis stage (**A**) and 40 DAP fruits (**D**). **B; E:** Confocal images of the Fluorescent brightener-28 stained equatorial ovary sections (**B**) and DAPI stained equatorial pericarp sections (**E**) used for computational measurements of E1 cell (marked with the yellow arrows) length (size bars are $100\mu\text{m}$; ab- indicates the abaxial side). **C; F:** Box plot charts displaying the distributions and the average E1 cell length of M82 (blue) and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (dark-

green) ovaries at the anthesis stage (C) and 40DAP pericarps (F). In A; C; D; F: Large dots and numbers next to each box plot represent the mean value of the respective genotype; small dots represent individual observations. Student's-t-test H_0 probabilities are presented as (n.s) (p-value) > 0.05; (**) (p-value) ≤ 0.01; (****) (p-value) ≤ 0.0001. In A,D: the number of measured ovaries /fruits =30. In C, F: The number of measured E1 cells = 100 (10 ovaries /fruits ten cells each).

Supplementary Figure S2: Comparison of the abaxial –adaxial cell layer numbers in M82 and 35S:amiR-TKN-II anthesis stage ovary wall, 10 and 40 DAP pericarps. Box plot chart displaying the distributions of the abaxial-adaxial ovary wall/pericarp cell layers (Y-axis) at 0 DAP (anthesis stage), 10DAP, and 40DAP (X-axis) M82 (blue) and 35S:amiR-TKN-II (dark green) ovaries/fruits. Large dots and numbers next to each box plot represent the mean value of the respective genotype; small dots represent individual observations. The letters above the box plots indicate statistical differences between the genotypes. Different letters indicate Student’s-t-test p-values ≤ 0.05, the similar letters indicate p-values > 0.05. The number of measured ovaries/fruits =40 for each genotype and stage.

Supplementary Figure S3: Representative IMARIS reconstructed confocal images used for the histological analysis of the M82 and 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* pericarps. **A:** Images of the 10DAP equatorial pericarp sections (top panels) indicating differences at the exocarp (E) layers number and structure between the M82 (left panel) and 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* (right panel) pericarps shown in close up insert at the bottom. Yellow arrows point to longitudinally oriented cell layers at the exocarp region of the 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* pericarps. **B:** Images of the 20 DAP M82 (left panel) and 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* equatorial pericarp sections (right panel). **C:** Images of the 40DAP M82 (left panel) and 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* equatorial pericarp sections (right panel). In **A-C:** Cell anatomy (white) was visualized using Fluorescent brightener-28 staining to highlight cell walls. Cell count was assisted by the Propidium-Iodide staining (red) to highlight cell walls and nuclei. Pericarp layers are named according to (Renaudin et al., 2017) as *E*- exocarp, *M'*-upper mesocarp, *M*- lower mesocarp, *I* – endocarp. The size bars in all panels = 1mm. At the insert panel of **A**, the size bar is 100 μ m.

A

B

Supplementary Figure S4: Comparison of the GA metabolic, catabolic, and response regulators transcription levels in M82 and 35S:amiR-TKN-II pericarps. **A:** Cube plot summaries of the absolute expression levels (Reads Per Million-RPM –represented by the color scale bar) of the fruit expressed GA metabolic (*SIGA20OX*), GA catabolic (*SIGA2OX*), and response regulator *PROCERA* in different tissues and at different developmental stages of the M82 fruits. The X-axes represent developmental stages. The z-axes represent different fruit tissues. Rows representing the pericarp expression are highlighted with the black frame. Data is acquired from the TEA atlas (<https://tea.solgenomics.net>). **B:** Line plots displaying RT-qPCR detected relative expression levels (RQ) of the *SIGA20OX* metabolic (top-panel), *SIGA2OX* catabolic (middle panel), and GA response regulator *PROCERA* (bottom panel) in developing M82 (blue) and 35S:amiR-TKN-II (dark green) pericarps. The Y-axes represent the Relative Expression levels. The X-axes represent the pericarp developmental stage in Days After Pollination (DAP). The dots represent mean values. Error bars represent standard errors. Student's t-test results of the expression level means-comparisons are indicated above each developmental time point as (n.s) (p-value) > 0.05; (*) (p-value) ≤ 0.05; (**) (p-value) ≤ 0.01; (***) (p-value) ≤ 0.001; n.d –indicates data points at which the gene expression levels could not be reliably determined by RT-qPCR.

Supplementary Figure S5: Leaf and fruit phenotypes induced by the genetic manipulation of the GA response. A: Leaf phenotypes of M82; *procera* (*pro*) loss-of-function 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* and 35S:*amiR-TKN-II pro* plants, showing an epistatic effect of the *pro*-loss-of function mutant on the 35S:*amiR-TKN-II* leaf shape. **B:** Fruit phenotypes induced by the ectopic miss-expression of the *POCERAΔ17* (*PROΔ17*) gene constitutively blocking the GA response (Nir et al., 2017). In **A-B:** The size bar = 6cm.

Supplementary Figure S6: Ovary wall and pericarp cytological phenotypes caused by the genetic interaction between the *pro*-loss-of-function mutant and TKN-II down-regulation. **A:** Confocal images of the fluorescent brightener-28 stained M82, *pro*, *35S:amiR-TKN-CL-II*, and *35S:amiR-TKN-II pro* anthesis stage ovary walls presented in the individual panels. The ovary wall abaxial side is indicated with the **ab** the adaxial size is indicated with the **ad**. The arrows point at the ovary wall E1 cells. The size bar in each panel = 50µm. **(B)** Box plots representing the distributions of the abaxial-adaxial cell layers. **C:** Box plots presenting the number of the epidermal cells across the equatorial perimeter. **D:** Box plots presenting the average length of the epidermal cells at the Anthesis stage ovaries. **E:** Box plots presenting the average length of the epidermal cells at the 40 DAP fruits. In B-E the genotypes are indicated as M82 (blue), *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (dark-green), *pro* (marigold), and *35S:amiR-TKN-II pro* (marine-green). Large dots and numbers next to each box plot represent the mean value of the respective genotype, small dots represent individual observations. The letters above the box plots indicate statistical differences between the genotypes. Different letters indicate Student's-t-test p-values (adjusted using Benjamini–Hochberg method) ≤ 0.05 , the similar letters indicate p-values > 0.05 .

Ploidy levels of 40 DAP pericarps

Supplementary Figure S7: Box plots presenting ploidy distributions of the nuclei from the equatorial pericarps of 40DAP - M82 (blue), 35S:amiR-TKN-II (dark green), *procera* (*pro*) (marigold), and 35S:amiR-TKN-II *procera* (marine-green) fruits. Large dots at each box represent the mean values; small dots represent individual observations. The X-axis panels indicate nuclei ploidy levels; the Y-axis show percent of the nucleus in the sampled tissue. The red arrow indicates 512C nuclei detected only in the *pro* mutants. Means comparison was performed separately for each ploidy level. Different letters at each ploidy panel indicate results of means comparison Student's-t-test p-values (adjusted using Benjamini–Hochberg method) ≤ 0.05 ; the similar letters indicate p-values > 0.05 . The number of sampled fruits for each genotype is ≥ 5 .

Supplementary Figure S8: Phenotypes induced by the ectopic application of Gibberellin (GA₃) to developing tomato fruits. **A:** Toluidine blue stained fresh tissue equatorial sections of the M82 (top panel) and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (bottom panel) untreated (left column) and treated with 40 ppm GA₃ pericarps. The images show an increase in the sizes of the pericarp cells induced by the ectopic GA application. The size bars are 1mm. **B:** Box plots displaying the distributions of untreated and treated (40 ppm GA₃) M82 (blue color; left panel) and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (dark-green; right panel) 40 DAP fruit weights. **C:** Images of the untreated and treated (40 ppm GA₃) M82 and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* 40 DAP fruits. The size bar is 6cm. **D:** Box plots displaying the distributions of untreated and treated (40 ppm GA₃) M82 (blue color; left panel) and *35S:amiR-TKN-II* (dark-green; right panel) 40 DAP fruit shape indexes. In **B**;**D**: Large dots and numbers next to the box plots indicate the average value for each genotype and treatment. Student's t-test results are indicated as (n.s) (p-value)> 0.05, n ≥ 10 fruits for each observation.